

The SOM Numbers (part II)

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Abstract: This preprint embarks on an innovative journey to expand the conventional understanding of even functions beyond the typical scope of quadratic functions. We propose a broader exploration, incorporating the oblong function, defined as $Y[y] = y^2 - y$, into the realm of even functions. This study not only redefines the traditional classifications within number theory but also introduces a novel perspective by considering zero as a composite number and both positive and negative integers as potential prime numbers, inspired by the study 'Integers are only Primes and Composites.' This preliminary work serves as a foundation for the development of an Atlas of Composite Generators for polynomials with degrees greater than 2 and highlights the potential of quadratic functions in creating a sieve for prime numbers. As an initial foray into this field, the study acknowledges the need for further development and refinement to fully realize its innovative potential.

Keywords: Even Functions, Oblong Function, Number Theory, Prime Numbers, Composite Generators, Quadratic Functions, Mathematical Symmetry.

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1 Introduction

Consider integers as passengers on an infinite aircraft. Square numbers would serve as the pilot, oblong numbers as the co-pilot, and the (square minus one) numbers would act as the flight engineer. The aircraft itself would represent the set of non-integer numbers, complementing the universe of numbers.

This study represents an initial preprint, laying the groundwork for a more profound and comprehensive exploration of even functions in mathematics, particularly challenging the traditional perception that is often limited to quadratic functions. By recognizing that other functions, such as the oblong function defined as $Y[y] = y^2 \pm y$, also satisfy the definition of an even function (see <https://www.mersenneforum.org/showpost.php?p=647085&postcount=67>), we expand our understanding of mathematical symmetries. This inclusion can offer new insights into the analysis of even functions, highlighting aspects frequently overlooked.

Although this work already introduces fundamental concepts and methodologies, it is important to emphasize its preliminary nature. The current study is incomplete and requires further development and elaboration. In this context, we address terms such as Taylor shift, Eureka Shift, Offset, DES-type, and SUB-type. Taylor shift, Eureka Shift, Offset, DES-type, SUB-type, and others. For a deeper understanding, we recommend consulting ‘Shift, Symmetry, and Asymmetry in Polynomials’ [27] and ‘C000000 Conventions, notations, abbreviations, glossary, and references’[20],

Furthermore, this preprint introduces a novel perspective in the classification of integers, inspired by the study ‘Integers are only Primes and Composites’ [26], proposing a more inclusive approach by considering 0 as a composite number and the positive and negative elements of the sequence ‘Prime numbers at the beginning of the 20th century’ <https://oeis.org/A008578> as prime numbers.

This initial study briefly introduces our Atlas of Composite Generators for polynomials of degree greater than 2 and outlines how quadratic functions can be used to create a sieve for prime numbers. We continue to work on expanding and refining these ideas, aiming to make a significant contribution to number theory and beyond.

2 The Common Differences Method and the Triangular Algorithm

The three basic quadratic theorems outlined in ‘The SOM Numbers (Part I)’ [23] exemplify the principle of the method of common differences [3] as applied to polynomials. This principle is further explored through an algorithm, which we shall refer to as the "Triangular Algorithm." The structure of this algorithm is visualized as follows:

Figure 1. The Triangular Algorithm of the SOM Numbers over the “Repunits Triangle”.

In this algorithm, each row represents a step in calculating an element of a quadratic sequence. The first position on the left of each row is termed the "initial element," which, in the case of our three basic quadratic theorems, is invariably the number 1. From this element, a constant value, known as the "step", is added to each subsequent element in the same row. For instance, if the step is 1, the second row will comprise the elements 1 and 2, the third row will have 1, 2, and 3, and so on.

The intriguing aspect of this algorithm is that, by summing the values in each row, we obtain an element that is part of a quadratic sequence. This results because the partial sum of each row is the outcome of two sums. Each iteration of "common" sums increases the degree of the resultant sequence. This is due to it being the reverse path of the common difference’s method. Each time we apply the common differences of a polynomial's elements, we find a new polynomial one degree lower. The common sums thus trace the reverse path in polynomial degree.

On a more cultural note, if we dare to be a bit bold in historical interpretation, we might call this algorithm the "Tetractys Triangle Algorithm." For a more mathematical description, the term "Repunits Triangle" would be fitting, as the triangle's structure and the number of elements in each row resemble the repunits sequence (as indicated at <https://oeis.org/A002275>).

See the following examples.

2.1 For Triangular Numbers:

- The primary differences are the sequence of positive integers (n): 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, ...
- The secondary differences are uniformly constant: 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, ...
- Consequently, the coefficient (a) in the quadratic equation for triangular numbers is deduced as $a = \frac{1}{2} = 0.5$.

- In the Triangular Algorithm, each row comprising positive integers culminates in the formation of triangular numbers.
- With an initial index ($i = 1$) and step increment of 1:

Figure 2. Summation of each row yields a triangular number. Variations in sums between consecutive rows, highlighted in red, correspond to integer values, exemplifying the primary differences in the polynomial $Y[y] = \frac{y^2 - y}{2}$ polynomial.

2.2 For Square Numbers:

- The initial differences constitute positive odd integers. The sequence follows $2n + 1$: 1, 3, 5, 7, ...
- The secondary differences remain constant at two: 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, ...
- Thus, the coefficient (a) in the quadratic equation for square numbers is ascertained as $a = \frac{2}{2} = 1$.
- The Triangular Algorithm operates with rows of positive odd numbers, with the summation of rows generating square numbers.
- Setting the initial index ($i = 1$) and step increment to 2:

Figure 3. Each row's summation results in a square number. The differential between row sums, marked in red, consists of odd numbers, displaying the primary differences in the polynomial $Y[y] = y^2$.

2.3 For Oblong Numbers:

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- The 1st differences are sequential positive even integers ($2n$: 0, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, ...).
- The 2nd differences are consistently two (2, 2, 2, 2, 2, ...).
- The coefficient $a = \frac{2}{2} = 1$.

- The Triangular Algorithm: Rows comprise positive even numbers, and the sums of these rows define oblong numbers.
- Initial value $i = 0$, step=2.

Figure 4. The summation of each row results in oblong numbers. The differences between the sums of consecutive rows, indicated in black, reveal the first differences in the method of common differences for the quadratic equation $Y[y] = y^2 \pm y$.

2.4 Conclusions:

A critical understanding gleaned from the examination of the last three figures is their foundational basis in illustrating the principle of the finite difference method for polynomials, particularly in the context of quadratic sequences.

Triangular Numbers:

- The first differences in triangular numbers are identified as positive integers, following the sequence n : 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, ...
- The second differences are uniformly constant at 1 (1, 1, 1, 1, 1, ...).
- Consequently, the coefficient (a) in the quadratic equation for triangular sequences is determined to be $a = \frac{1}{2} = 0.5$.

Square Numbers:

- For square numbers, the first differences are positive odd integers, adhering to the pattern $2n + 1$: 1, 3, 5, 7, ...
- The second differences maintain a constant value of 2 (2, 2, 2, 2, 2, ...).
- Therefore, the coefficient (a) in the quadratic equation for square sequences is calculated as $a = \frac{2}{2} = 1$.

Oblong Numbers:

- The first differences in oblong numbers are characterized as positive even integers, following the formula $2n$: 0, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, ...
- The second differences, akin to square numbers, are consistently at 2 (2, 2, 2, 2, 2, ...).
- This results in the coefficient (a) for the quadratic oblong sequence equation being $a = \frac{2}{2} = 1$.

The analysis reveals that since triangular numbers exhibit the smallest possible second difference among integers, it is implausible to have a quadratic sequence of integers with a coefficient $a < 0.5$. Similarly, no quadratic sequence of integers with a coefficient $a = 1$ can

exist without being established either on the first differences of squares or the first differences of oblongs.

Extending this notion, if the second differences are consistently three (3, 3, 3, 3, 3, ...), then the coefficient (a) for the quadratic sequence equation is deduced to be $a = \frac{3}{2} = 1.5$. This implies the existence of three distinct quadratics with differing first differences represented by positive integers in the form: $(3n)$, $(3n+1)$, $(3n+2)$.

Similarly, with a second difference consistently at four (4, 4, 4, 4, 4, ...), the coefficient (a) is ascertained to be $a = \frac{4}{2} = 2$, indicating four distinct quadratic forms with first differences represented by positive integers: $(4n)$, $(4n+1)$, $(4n+2)$, $(4n+3)$, and so forth.

This reflection directly limits the production of diverse polynomial sequences of integers to a finite number. With additional levels of differences, analogous patterns emerge in polynomials of higher degrees.

This is fully in accordance with the tables in the Atlas under the sections '10.4 Method of Differences Analysis (Figure 19)', and '10.5 Fundamental Table of Quadratic CGs (Figure 20)' explored in 'The SOM Numbers (Part I)' [23].

For triangular numbers, the sequence of second differences is a series of 1's, representing the smallest possible second difference in quadratics. Thus, it is infeasible to have a quadratic sequence of integers with a coefficient $a = \frac{1}{2} = 0.5$. This denotes a singular quadratic form where the first difference results in positive integers (n).

In the case of square and oblong numbers, any quadratic sequence of integers with a coefficient ($a = 1$) must inherently rely on either the first difference of squares or the first difference of oblongs, given that the coefficient ($a = 1$) yields a second difference sequence of 2's.

Introducing a constant (c) allows for the creation of an infinite number of quadratics in forms such as *square* $\pm c$ and *oblong* $\pm c$. However, these primarily represent a horizontal Eureka shift, categorizing them as either SUB or DES type quadratics, with no ACC quadratic type at ($a = 1$).

Further exploration of second differences, such as a consistent sequence of 3's, 4's, and beyond, continues to reveal a similar pattern, underscoring the method's applicability and scope in formulating quadratic sequences of higher coefficients.

3 Analysis of Symmetry in Quadratic Sequences and Their Relationship with Taylor Shifts

This paragraph delves into the significant distinction between symmetric and asymmetric quadratic sequences and how this distinction impacts the analysis of unique forms of sequences and Taylor shifts.

3.1 Symmetry in Quadratic Sequences

The parabolic curve of the form $x = ay^2 + by + c$ exhibits symmetry around its vertex, regardless of being part of a symmetric or asymmetric integer sequence. This symmetry remains constant with respect to the second-degree coefficient 'a'. In symmetric quadratic sequences, the vertex of the parabola must have either an integer y-coordinate or a semi-odd value that is half of an odd number $\frac{odd}{2}$, leading to two types of symmetry:

- **SUB-Type:** When y_{vertex} is an integer, the corresponding x_{vertex} value is also an integer. The sequence symmetrically distributes around the vertex, duplicating all elements except the one at the vertex (x_{vertex}).
- **DES-Type:** With $y_{vertex} = \frac{odd}{2}$, then x_{vertex} value is not an integer, resulting in duplicated elements along both parabolic lines without exception.

3.2 Symmetric Sequences and Uniqueness

In symmetric sequences, the order of values remains consistent, regardless of the direction of the y index. All parabolic curves are symmetric in relation to their vertex point. When this parabolic curve, which is always symmetric, has the y_{vertex} as either an integer or a semi-odd number, it generates a symmetric sequence of quadratic integers. This results in sequences where the order of values is the same, regardless of the reading direction. We can always choose a direction for reading the sequence elements such that the values are decreasing. Eventually, we reach an element that is the lowest value among all others. From this element, we may find at most one other element equal to this lowest value, and then the sequence starts presenting increasing values identical to the decreasing ones. The constant repetition of values in the increasing and decreasing parts of the sequence defines its symmetry. If there is a single element lower than all other repeating elements, the sequence is a SUB-type. If there are two equal elements that are the lowest among all other repeating elements, the sequence is a DES-type.

In such symmetric sequences, considering direct and inverse sequences as equivalent does not affect the number of unique forms, as they are identical by nature.

3.3 Asymmetry and Reverse Sequences

Asymmetric quadratic sequences are characterized by a y_{vertex} value that is neither an integer nor a semi-odd number, creating an asymmetric distribution in the XY plane. Each side of the parabolic curve generates unique, non-repeated elements. Such asymmetry in the distribution relative to Cartesian coordinates means that each side of the parabola divided by the vertex produces non-repeating integer elements, defining the sequence as asymmetric. Simultaneously, if we define $x = ay^2 + by + c$ as the direct sequence, then $x = ay^2 - by + c$ immediately becomes the reverse sequence. Both sequences contain the same elements but in reverse order.

Considering a sequence and its inverse as identical leads to a reduction in the total number of unique sequence forms. For example, a generated sequence $\{2, 4, 7, 11, \dots\}$ and its inverse $\{\dots,$

11, 7, 4, 2} are considered the same, thus reducing the count of unique forms. This is in alignment with the Atlas of quadratic sequences seen in item ‘10.5 Fundamental Table of Quadratic CGs (Figure 20)’ [23].

3.4 Mathematical Conclusions

Differentiating between symmetric and asymmetric sequences is crucial in the analysis of Taylor shifts in quadratic sequences. While the reduction in the number of unique forms applies to asymmetric sequences, symmetric sequences remain unaffected due to their spontaneous symmetry. This deepened understanding offers a more precise perspective on the properties of quadratic sequences, emphasizing the importance of symmetry in the analysis of Taylor shifts and in identifying unique forms of sequences.

For each coefficient a , the possible value of the Taylor shift step h varies accordingly. Therefore, we observe the following relationship:

- If $a = \frac{1}{2}$, then $y_{sp} = b$. Hence, Taylor shift step is $h = 1$.
- If $a = 1$, then $y_{sp} = \frac{b}{2}$. Hence, Taylor shift step is $h = \frac{1}{2}$.
- If $a = 1,5$, then $y_{sp} = \frac{b}{3}$. Hence, Taylor shift step is $h = \frac{1}{3}$.
- If $a = 2$, then $y_{sp} = \frac{b}{4}$. Hence, Taylor shift step is $h = \frac{1}{4}$.
- If $a = 2,5$, then $y_{sp} = \frac{b}{5}$. Hence, Taylor shift step is $h = \frac{1}{5}$.
- If $a = 3$, then $y_{sp} = \frac{b}{6}$. Hence, Taylor shift step is $h = \frac{1}{6}$.
- If $a = 3,5$, then $y_{sp} = \frac{b}{7}$. Hence, Taylor shift step is $h = \frac{1}{7}$.
- And so on.

As a result, for quadratic equations with different coefficients $\backslash(a)$, we have:

- Quadratics with $a=0.5$ we have 1 single form of Taylor shifts.
- Quadratics with $a=1.0$ we have 2 unique forms of Taylor shifts.
- Quadratics with $a=1.5$ we have 3 unique forms of Taylor shifts.
- Quadratics with $a=2.0$ we have 4 unique forms of Taylor shifts.
- Quadratics with $a=2.5$ we have 5 unique forms of Taylor shifts.
- Quadratics with $a=3.0$ we have 6 unique forms of Taylor shifts.
- Quadratics with $a=3.5$ we have 7 unique forms of Taylor shifts.
- And so on.

When considering direct sequences as identical to their reverses, we obtain:

- Quadratics with $a=0.5$ we have 1 single sequence form.
- Quadratics with $a=1.0$ we have 2 unique sequence forms.
- Quadratics with $a=1.5$ we have 2 unique sequence forms.
- Quadratics with $a=2.0$ we have 3 unique sequence forms.
- Quadratics with $a=2.5$ we have 3 unique sequence forms.
- Quadratics with $a=3.0$ we have 4 unique sequence forms.

- Quadratics with $a=3.5$ we have 4 unique sequence forms.
- And so on.

4 Symmetry Types in Even and Odd Functions

This analysis delves into the symmetrical properties of square and oblong numbers, with a focus on their classification as even functions and the implications for their symmetry.

4.1 Symmetry in Square Numbers:

- The sequence of square numbers, as defined in the OEIS sequence <https://oeis.org/A000290>, is represented by the even function $Y[y] = y^2$.
- If $Y[y] = y^2$, then $Y[-y] = y^2$ also holds true.
- Given $Y[y] = Y[-y]$, the function for square numbers is an even function demonstrating SUB-type symmetry, indicating symmetry around the X-axis.

4.2 Symmetry in Oblong Numbers:

- Oblong numbers, referenced in the OEIS sequence <https://oeis.org/A002378>, are defined by the even function $Y[y] = y^2 - y$.
- For oblong numbers, $Y[y] = y^2 - y$ implies $Y[-y] = y^2 + y$.
- Because $Y[y] \neq Y[-y]$, oblong numbers do not display SUB-type symmetry.
- However, $Y[y + 1] = (y + 1)^2 - (y + 1) = y^2 + y$, thus $Y[y + 1] = Y[-y]$ means oblong numbers are characterized by DES-type symmetric even function, differing from square numbers.

4.3 Exploring Symmetry in Odd Functions:

- Considering the integer number sequence $\{\dots, -3, -2, -1, 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$ from OEIS <https://oeis.org/A256958>, defined by the odd function property $Y[y] = -Y[-y]$, we observe a duplication of all elements in their absolute values, except for 0, which is not duplicated, classifying it as an odd SUB-type function.
- The distinct property for the element 0, where $Y[y] = \pm Y[-y] = 0$, is unique to SUB-type sequences in odd functions, due to 0 being the only integer without a positive or negative sign.

4.4 Does the DES-Type Symmetry Exist in Odd Functions?

- Considering integers as "semi-even" numbers, i.e., even numbers divided by 2, we establish:

$$\frac{\{ \dots, -6, -4, -2, 0, 2, 4, 6, \dots \}}{2} = \{ \dots, -3, -2, -1, 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots \}$$

- If integers are semi-even numbers (even numbers divided by 2), then what are the semi-odd numbers (odd numbers divided by 2)?

$$\frac{2y - 1}{2} = y - 0.5$$

$$\frac{\{\dots, -5, -3, -1, 0, 1, 3, 5, \dots\}}{2} = \{\dots, -2.5, -1.5, -0.5, 0.5, 1.5, 2.5, \dots\}$$

- This demonstrates that odd functions also possess DES-type sequences. Therefore, the same definitional constraints found in even functions apply to odd functions. We need to extend the definition of odd functions to $Y[y] = -Y[-y + 1]$ or $Y[-y] = -Y[y + 1]$.

5 Symmetry and Sequences: Exploring Base 10 Through Square and Oblong Numbers

Introduction

In our exploration of number theory, drawing upon the unconventional definitions from the study ‘Integers are only Primes and Composites’, we extend the traditional classification of prime numbers to include ± 1 and treat both positive and negative integers as potential primes. This expanded perspective allows us to delve into the intricate relationship between base 10 digits, square numbers, and oblong numbers.

Square numbers, defined as products of two identical integers, and oblong numbers, as products of two consecutive integers (either direction, i.e., $x=y(y\pm 1)$), provide a framework for examining the base 10 digits through mathematical patterns and relationships.

1. Zero and the Notion of Identity:

Zero (0) stands uniquely as it can be expressed as the difference between any two identical products: $0 = x * y - x * y$.

2. The Singular Nature of ± 1 :

The number 1, being the first positive integer, is prime in its form as a square minus zero ($1^2 - 0^2$).

Likewise, -1, the negative counterpart, emerges as prime in the form of a square minus one or the negative of a square plus zero ($-1^2 + 0^2$).

3. The Role of 2 as an Oblong Prime:

The number 2 manifests as the first and only prime oblong number, conforming to the pattern of an oblong minus zero ($2(2 - 1) - 1(1 - 1)$).

4. Three and its Unique Position:

Three (3), the first positive integer in the form of a square minus one ($3 = 2^2 - 1^2$), is the sole prime in this format.

Negative three (-3), is the only (-square plus 1) number that is prime ($-4 + 1 = -3$).

5. Four and Even Composite Nature:

The number 4, as the first positive integer in the form of an oblong minus two ($4 = 3(3 - 1) - 2(2 - 1)$), leads us to a general rule: all numbers in this form are even and composite, given that all oblong numbers are even.

6. Five, Seven, and Their Prime Forms:

Numbers like 5 and 7, being the first positive integers in the form of a square minus four ($5 = 3^2 - 2^2$) and a square minus nine ($7 = 4^2 - 3^2$) respectively, are primes unique to these forms.

7. The Composite Nature of Six, Eight, and Higher Even Numbers:

Numbers such as 6 and 8, representing the first integers in the form of an oblong minus six ($6 = 4(4 - 1) - 3(3 - 1)$) and an oblong minus twelve ($8 = 5(5 - 1) - 4(4 - 1)$), reinforce the rule: such numbers are invariably even and composite.

8. Nine and Its Composite Classification:

Nine (9) highlights its odd square composite nature in multiple forms: as a square minus sixteen ($9 = 5^2 - 4^2$) and as a square minus zero ($9 = 3^2 - 0^2$), highlighting the multifaceted relationships in these numerical structures.

This study embarks on a journey across the number line, employing these properties to unveil the nuanced and often overlooked patterns embedded within the fundamental structure of integers. Our investigation promises to shed new light on the symmetries, asymmetries, and inherent beauty of numbers, driven by a broader and more inclusive definition of primality.

5.1 Conclusion: Unveiling Prime Numbers Through Quadratic Sieves

Our comprehensive study leads to a nuanced understanding of how prime numbers, both positive and negative, manifest within specific quadratic forms. This understanding serves as an effective sieve in identifying and categorizing prime numbers.

1. Odd Number Representation:

Upon examining the structure of odd numbers, we find that all positive and negative odd integers exclusively fit into the format of a square sequence minus a square number. This is elaborated in section 6.3, "Offset in Partial Sum and Integral of the Odds."

2. Even Number Representation:

Similarly, all positive and negative even integers can be expressed in the format of an oblong sequence minus an oblong number, as detailed in section 7.5, "Offset in Partial Sum and Integral of the Evens."

3. Characterization of Positive Odd Prime Numbers:

A crucial discovery is that all positive odd prime numbers uniquely appear in only one quadratic form $y(y + 2b)$. This exclusivity distinguishes them from composites, which are found in multiple forms. This singular appearance in a specific quadratic form becomes a defining characteristic of positive odd primes.

4. Uniqueness of the Prime Number 2:

Prime number 2, the only positive even prime, is characterized by its presence in a singular quadratic form $y(y + (2b - 1))$ and its absence from any other forms $y(y + b)$. This property sets it apart from positive even composite numbers.

A unique aspect of our study is the special relationship of the number 2 with the distribution of prime numbers, especially in the context of twin primes. Twin primes, pairs of consecutive primes differing by 2, highlight the distinct position of 2.

Notably, the number 2 uniquely resides between the square number 1 and the number 3 (one less than a square). This singularity, applying to both 2 and -2 , is not observed elsewhere on the number line, where one twin prime is a square number, and the other is one less than a square.

This peculiar positioning of the number 2 between these specific numerical forms underscores a distinct pattern in the distribution of prime numbers, emphasizing its special role in the realm of twin primes.

(see post <https://www.mersenneforum.org/showpost.php?p=644843&postcount=26>).

5. Identification of Positive Odd Composites:

Contrasting with primes, all positive odd composite numbers are identified by their appearance in two or more quadratic forms $y(y + 2b)$. This multiplicity in representation is a clear indicator of their composite nature.

6. Categorization of Positive Even Composites:

The positive even composite numbers are similarly characterized by appearing in two or more quadratic forms $y(y + 2b + 1)$, and/or $y(y + 2b)$. This pattern distinctly separates them from prime numbers.

This comprehensive investigation not only reinforces the unique properties of primes and composites in the context of quadratic sequences but also uncovers new patterns in the distribution and positioning of prime numbers, particularly in relation to the number 2 and twin primes. Our study opens new avenues for understanding the distribution and nature of prime numbers through the lens of quadratic forms, offering a valuable tool for further exploration in number theory.

6 Introduction to Composite Generators of Higher Degrees

First, it is noteworthy that all these generators produce quadratic forms from 1st-degree polynomials. This phenomenon arises because the partial sums of 1st-degree polynomials, such as odd or even sequences, result in quadratic polynomials, analogous to the integration process in calculus.

This principle extends to polynomials of any degree:

$$\sum_1^y y^0 = \frac{0!y}{1!}$$

$$\sum_1^y y^1 = \frac{1!y^2}{2!} + Y1[y]$$

$$\sum_1^y y^2 = \frac{2!y^3}{3!} + Y2[y]$$

$$\sum_1^y y^3 = \frac{3!y^4}{4!} + Y3[y]$$

$$\sum_1^y y^4 = \frac{4!y^5}{5!} + Y4[y]$$

$$\sum_1^y y^5 = \frac{5!y^6}{6!} + Y5[y]$$

...

$$\sum_1^y y^d = \frac{d!y^{(d+1)}}{(d+1)!} + Yd[y] = \frac{y^{(d+1)}}{d+1} + Yd[y]$$

The complete sums are expressed as:

$$\sum_{k=1}^y k^0 = y$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^y k^1 = \frac{y(y+1)}{2}$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^y k^2 = \frac{y(y+1)(2y+1)}{6}$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^y k^3 = \frac{y^2(y+1)^2}{4}$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^y k^4 = \frac{y(y+1)(2y+1)(3y^2+3y-1)}{30}$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^y k^5 = \frac{y^2(y+1)^2(2y^2+2y-1)}{12}$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^y k^6 = \frac{y(y+1)(2y+1)(3y^4+6y^3-3y+1)}{42}$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^y k^7 = \frac{y^2(y+1)^2(3y^4+6y^3-y^2-4y+2)}{24}$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^y k^8 = \frac{y(y+1)(2y+1)(5y^6+15y^5+5y^4-15y^3-y^2+9y-3)}{90}$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^y k^9 = \frac{y^2(y+1)^2(y^2+y-1)(2y^4+4y^3-y^2-3y+3)}{20}$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^y k^{10} = \frac{y(y+1)(2y+1)(y^2+y-1)(3y^6+9y^5+2y^4-11y^3+3y^2+10y-5)}{66}$$

Observe how the partial sums evolve with increasing degrees:

$$\sum_{k=1}^y k^0 = y = \frac{0!}{1!}y$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^y k^1 = y \frac{(y+1)}{2} = \frac{1!}{2!}(y+1) \sum_{k=1}^y k^0$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^y k^2 = \frac{y(y+1)(2y+1)}{6} = \frac{y(y+1)}{2} * \frac{(2y+1)}{3} = \frac{(2y+1)}{3} \sum_{k=1}^y k^1 = \frac{2!}{3!}(2y+1) \sum_{k=1}^y k^1$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^y k^3 = \frac{y^2(y+1)^2}{4} = y \frac{(y+1)}{2} * y \frac{(y+1)}{2} = \sum_{k=1}^y k^1 * \sum_{k=1}^y k^1$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^y k^4 = \frac{y(y+1)(2y+1)(3y^2+3y-1)}{30} = \frac{y(y+1)(2y+1)}{6} * \frac{(3y^2+3y-1)}{5} = \frac{(3y^2+3y-1)}{5} \sum_{k=1}^y k^2$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^y k^5 = \frac{y^2(y+1)^2(2y^2+2y-1)}{12} = \frac{y^2(y+1)^2}{4} * \frac{(2y^2+2y-1)}{3} = \frac{(2y^2+2y-1)}{3} * \sum_{k=1}^y k^3$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{k=1}^y k^6 &= \frac{y(y+1)(2y+1)(3y^4+6y^3-3y+1)}{42} = \frac{y(y+1)(2y+1)}{6} * \frac{(3y^4+6y^3-3y+1)}{7} \\
\sum_{k=1}^y k^7 &= \frac{y^2(y+1)^2(3y^4+6y^3-y^2-4y+2)}{24} = \frac{y^2(y+1)^2}{4} * \frac{(3y^4+6y^3-y^2-4y+2)}{6} \\
\sum_{k=1}^y k^8 &= \frac{y(y+1)(2y+1)(5y^6+15y^5+5y^4-15y^3-y^2+9y-3)}{90} \\
&= \frac{y(y+1)(2y+1)}{6} * \frac{(5y^6+15y^5+5y^4-15y^3-y^2+9y-3)}{15} \\
\sum_{k=1}^y k^9 &= \frac{y^2(y+1)^2(y^2+y-1)(2y^4+4y^3-y^2-3y+3)}{20} = \frac{y^2(y+1)^2}{4} * \frac{(y^2+y-1)(2y^4+4y^3-y^2-3y+3)}{5} \\
\sum_{k=1}^y k^{10} &= \frac{y(y+1)(2y+1)(y^2+y-1)(3y^6+9y^5+2y^4-11y^3+3y^2+10y-5)}{66} \\
&= \frac{y(y+1)(2y+1)}{6} * \frac{(y^2+y-1)(3y^6+9y^5+2y^4-11y^3+3y^2+10y-5)}{11}
\end{aligned}$$

Second, the algorithms generating these sums, which substantiate three theorems, employ a consistent "triangle form" of summation, varying only in the elements included in the sums. This triangular structure is reminiscent of the repunits triangle, also known as the Pascal's triangle format. The effectiveness of the methods of common differences and partial sums is attributed to this triangular configuration. Further exploration is warranted on how the method of differences manifests across all integer triangles.

7 Cubic Composite Generators (CGs)

Continuing from Part I, we explore increasing the polynomial degree to $d = 3$. The cubic CGs generated by squares are determined by the integral:

$$\int_f^y (y+h)^2 dy = \frac{1}{3}((h+y)^3 - (h+f)^3)$$

For oblong numbers, the corresponding integral is:

$$\begin{aligned}
&\int_f^y ((y+h)^2 - (y+h)) dy \\
&= \left(\frac{y^3}{3} + \left(h - \frac{1}{2} \right) y^2 + (h^2 - h)y \right) - \left(\frac{f^3}{3} + \left(h - \frac{1}{2} \right) f^2 + (h^2 - h)f \right)
\end{aligned}$$

The term $\left(h - \frac{1}{2} \right) y^2$ suggests that it remains possible for there to be a Taylor shift of $\frac{odd}{2}$.

The multiplicative term $\left(h - \frac{1}{2} \right)$ results from the term hy^2 from the integral $\int (y+h)^2 dy$ minus the term $\frac{y^2}{2}$ from the integral $\int (y+h) dy$.

$$\begin{aligned}
\int (y+h)^2 dy &= \frac{y^3}{3} + hy^2 + h^2y + \frac{h^3}{3} + c \\
\int (y+h) dy &= \frac{y^2}{2} + hy + c
\end{aligned}$$

Regarding the term $h^2 - h$?? (Rever o raciocínio. O cálculo está correto.)

8 The integrals producing polynomial sequences

We know that the integral of the constant 1 is

$$\int (1)dy = y + b$$

In this case, b may be any constant value. This is because for any pair of integers p and q , we get:

$$\int_p^q (1) dy = (q + b) - (p + b) = q - p = \text{integer}$$

The result is always an integer independently from the value of b .

Now,

$$\iint (1)dydy = \int (y + b)dy = \frac{y^2}{2} + by + c$$

So,

$$\int_p^q (y + b) dy = \frac{q^2 - p^2}{2} + b(q - p)$$

Now, the integer result will depend on b and independent from c .

$$\int_p^q (y + b) dy = \frac{q^2 - p^2}{2} + b(q - p) = (q - p) \left(\frac{q + p}{2} + b \right)$$

If $(p + q) = \text{odd}$, then we need $b = \frac{\text{odd}}{2}$ to get the integer as result of the integral.

If we want the integral to calculate partial sums, we need to calculate the integral step by step with successive $q = p + 1$. If $q = p + 1$, then $b = \pm 0.5$.

This is because:

$$\int_p^{p+1} (y + b) dy = \frac{(p + 1)^2 - p^2}{2} + b(p + 1 - p) = \frac{p^2 + 2p + 1 - p^2}{2} + b = p + \frac{1}{2} + b$$

If we want $\int_p^{p+1} (y + b) dy = \text{integer}$, then $b = \pm 0.5$.

Now,

$$\iint (1)dydy = \int (y \pm b)dy = \int \left(y \pm \frac{1}{2} \right) dy = \frac{y^2}{2} \pm \frac{y}{2} + c$$

And,

$$\begin{aligned} \iint_p^q (1)dydy &= \int_p^q (y + b)dy \\ \int_p^q (y + b) dy &= \frac{q^2 - p^2}{2} + b(q - p) \\ \int_p^q (y + b) dy &= \frac{q^2 - p^2}{2} + \frac{q - p}{2} \\ \int_p^q (y + b) dy &= \frac{q^2 + q}{2} - \frac{p^2 + p}{2} \end{aligned}$$

8.1 Integral does not change Taylor shift

When we compare the points of symmetry of a polynomial before and after its integral, we notice that the point of symmetry does not change with the integral.

$$Y1[y] = \int (a)dy = \frac{ay^1}{1} + b$$

$$Y2[y] = \int (ay + b)dy = \frac{ay^2}{2} + \frac{by^1}{1} + c$$

$$Y3[y] = \int (ay^2 + by + c)dy = \frac{ay^3}{3} + \frac{by^2}{2} + \frac{cy^1}{1} + d$$

$$Y4[y] = \int (ay^3 + by^2 + cy + d)dy = \frac{ay^4}{4} + \frac{by^3}{3} + \frac{cy^2}{2} + \frac{dy^1}{1} + e$$

$$Y5[y] = \int (ay^4 + by^3 + cy^2 + dy + e)dy = \frac{ay^5}{5} + \frac{by^4}{4} + \frac{cy^3}{3} + \frac{dy^2}{2} + \frac{ey^1}{1} + f$$

$$Y6[y] = \int (ay^5 + by^4 + cy^3 + dy^2 + ey^1 + f)dy \\ = \frac{ay^6}{6} + \frac{by^5}{5} + \frac{cy^4}{4} + \frac{dy^3}{3} + \frac{ey^2}{2} + \frac{fy^1}{1} + g$$

The Y-coordinates of the symmetry point in each integral is

$$y_{sp_{Y1[y]}} \left[@ \frac{d^0 Y1[y]}{dy^0} = 0 \right] = -\frac{a_0}{a_1} = -\frac{b}{\frac{1a}{1}} = -\frac{b}{a}$$

$$y_{sp_{Y2[y]}} \left[@ \frac{d^1 Y2[y]}{dy^1} = 0 \right] = -\frac{a_1}{2a_2} = -\frac{\frac{b}{1}}{\frac{2a}{2}} = -\frac{b}{a}$$

$$y_{sp_{Y3[y]}} \left[@ \frac{d^2 Y3[y]}{dy^2} = 0 \right] = -\frac{a_2}{3a_3} = -\frac{\frac{b}{2}}{\frac{3a}{3}} = -\frac{b}{2a}$$

$$y_{sp_{Y4[y]}} \left[@ \frac{d^3 Y4[y]}{dy^3} = 0 \right] = -\frac{a_3}{4a_4} = -\frac{\frac{b}{3}}{\frac{4a}{4}} = -\frac{b}{3a}$$

$$y_{sp_{Y5[y]}} \left[@ \frac{d^4 Y5[y]}{dy^4} = 0 \right] = -\frac{a_4}{5a_5} = -\frac{\frac{b}{4}}{\frac{5a}{5}} = -\frac{b}{4a}$$

$$y_{sp_{Y6[y]}} \left[@ \frac{d^5 Y6[y]}{dy^5} = 0 \right] = -\frac{a_5}{6a_6} = -\frac{\frac{b}{5}}{\frac{6a}{6}} = -\frac{b}{5a}$$

8.2 Successive Integrals

If we continue doing partial integrals is equivalent to do partial sums. We will get the Pascal's triangle?

$$Y1[y] = \int (a)dy = \frac{ay^1}{1!} + \frac{by^0}{0!}$$

$$Y2[y] = \int (ay + b)dy = \frac{ay^2}{2!} + \frac{by^1}{1!} + \frac{cy^0}{0!}$$

$$Y3[y] = \int \left(\frac{ay^2}{2} + by + c \right) dy = \frac{ay^3}{3!} + \frac{by^2}{2!} + \frac{cy^1}{1!} + \frac{dy^0}{0!}$$

$$Y4[y] = \int \left(\frac{ay^3}{6} + \frac{by^2}{2} + cy + d \right) dy = \frac{ay^4}{4!} + \frac{by^3}{3!} + \frac{cy^2}{2!} + \frac{dy^1}{1!} + \frac{ey^0}{0!}$$

$$Y5[y] = \int \left(\frac{ay^4}{24} + \frac{by^3}{6} + \frac{cy^2}{2} + dy + e \right) dy = \frac{ay^5}{5!} + \frac{by^4}{4!} + \frac{cy^3}{3!} + \frac{dy^2}{2!} + \frac{ey^1}{1!} + \frac{fy^0}{0!}$$

$$Y6[y] = \int \left(\frac{ay^5}{5!} + \frac{by^4}{4!} + \frac{cy^3}{3!} + \frac{dy^2}{2!} + \frac{ey^1}{1!} + \frac{fy^0}{0!} \right) dy \\ = \frac{ay^6}{6!} + \frac{by^5}{5!} + \frac{cy^4}{4!} + \frac{dy^3}{3!} + \frac{ey^2}{2!} + \frac{fy^1}{1!} + \frac{gy^0}{0!}$$

The Y-coordinates of the symmetry point in each integral is

$$y_{sp_{Y1[y]}} \left[@ \frac{d^0 Y1[y]}{dy^0} = 0 \right] = -\frac{a_0}{a_1} = -\frac{\frac{b}{0!}}{\frac{1a}{1!}} = -\frac{b}{a}$$

$$y_{sp_{Y2[y]}} \left[@ \frac{d^1 Y2[y]}{dy^1} = 0 \right] = -\frac{a_1}{2a_2} = -\frac{\frac{b}{1!}}{\frac{2a}{2!}} = -\frac{b}{a}$$

$$y_{sp_{Y3[y]}} \left[@ \frac{d^2 Y3[y]}{dy^2} = 0 \right] = -\frac{a_2}{3a_3} = -\frac{\frac{b}{2}}{\frac{3a}{3!}} = -\frac{b}{a}$$

$$y_{sp_{Y4[y]}} \left[@ \frac{d^3 Y4[y]}{dy^3} = 0 \right] = -\frac{a_3}{4a_4} = -\frac{\frac{b}{3!}}{\frac{4a}{4!}} = -\frac{b}{a}$$

$$y_{sp_{Y5[y]}} \left[@ \frac{d^4 Y5[y]}{dy^4} = 0 \right] = -\frac{a_4}{5a_5} = -\frac{\frac{b}{4!}}{\frac{5a}{5!}} = -\frac{b}{a}$$

$$y_{sp_{Y6[y]}} \left[@ \frac{d^5 Y6[y]}{dy^5} = 0 \right] = -\frac{a_5}{6a_6} = -\frac{\frac{b}{5!}}{\frac{6a}{6!}} = -\frac{b}{a}$$

https://oeis.org/A000004	https://oeis.org/A000012	https://oeis.org/A256958	https://oeis.org/a000217	https://oeis.org/a000292	https://oeis.org/a000332	https://oeis.org/a000389	https://oeis.org/a000579	https://oeis.org/a000580	https://oeis.org/a000581	https://oeis.org/a000582
d	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
$a_d=1/d!$	1/0!	1/1!	1/2!	1/3!	1/4!	1/5!	1/6!	1/7!	1/8!	1/9!
$y^d =$	y^0	y^1	y^2	y^3	y^4	y^5	y^6	y^7	y^8	y^9
SUB	DES	SUB	DES	SUB	DES	SUB	DES	SUB	DES	SUB
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
0	1	3	6	10	15	21	28	36	45	55
0	1	4	10	20	35	56	84	120	165	220
0	1	5	15	35	70	126	210	330	495	715
0	1	6	21	56	126	252	462	792	1287	2002
0	1	7	28	84	210	462	924	1716	3003	5005
0	1	8	36	120	330	792	1716	3432	6435	11440
0	1	9	45	165	495	1287	3003	6435	12870	24310
0	1	10	55	220	715	2002	5005	11440	24310	48620
0	1	11	66	286	1001	3003	8008	19448	43758	92378
0	1	12	78	364	1365	4368	12376	31824	75582	167960
0	1	13	91	455	1820	6188	18564	50388	125970	293930
0	1	14	105	560	2380	8568	27132	77520	203490	497420
0	1	15	120	680	3060	11628	38760	116280	319770	817190

Figure 5. Starting with a constant, in this case 1, Pascal's triangle generates polynomials of increasing degree from 0 to infinity.

9 Quartics as Products of Two Quadratics

Expanding on the technique used to develop quadratic Composite Generators (CGs), this approach can be extended to generate polynomial CGs of any degree. In this context, we outline key concepts that serve as foundational tools for further studies.

By adjusting coefficients a and b , we can manipulate the quadratic composite generator sequence $Y[y] = y(ay + b)$ to yield a desired integer value at a specific index y . Notably, some values of $Y[y]$ may be prime numbers. However, when two quadratic sequences are multiplied, the resultant product is typically a composite number. In the least favorable scenario, this product might be the prime number 1 or a semiprime.

To achieve an infinite series of prime numbers from the product of two quadratic sequences, a 'Eureka shift' can be applied, involving the addition of a constant. This concept is an extension of the discussions found at thread 'The oblong parabolic sieve of primes' <https://www.mersenneforum.org/showthread.php?t=28194>.

9.1 The Products of Two Square Numbers

The multiplication of any two square numbers invariably results in another square number. This is represented by the equation:

$$y^2 * (y + b_d)^2 = (y * (y + b_d))^2$$

Conclusion I:

Regardless of the value of b_d , the product $square[y] * square[y \pm b_d]$ always forms a square number. This relationship is encapsulated by the sequence:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{https://oeis.org/A000290}[y] * \text{https://oeis.org/A000290}[y + b_d] = \\ & \text{https://oeis.org/A000290}[y(y + b_d)]. \end{aligned}$$

9.2 The Products of Two Oblong Numbers

We examine the multiplication of two oblong numbers under different offsets. The oblong number is defined as $oblong[y] = y^2 \pm y$, depending on the offset.

9.2.1. Using offset $f = -1$:

Let us calculate $oblong[y] * oblong[y + b_d]$ for $oblong[y] = y^2 + y$ in offset $f = -1$:

$$(1) oblong[y] = y^2 + y$$

$$oblong[y + b_d] = (y + b_d)^2 + y + b_d$$

$$oblong[y + b_d] = y^2 + 2b_d y + b_d^2 + y + b_d$$

$$(2) oblong[y + b_d] = y^2 + (2b_d + 1)y + b_d^2 + b_d$$

So, (1) * (2) is:

$$oblong[y] * oblong[y + b_d] = (y^2 + y)(y^2 + (2b_d + 1)y + b_d^2 + b_d)$$

$$oblong[y] * oblong[y + b_d]$$

$$= y^4 + (2b_d + 1)y^3 + (b_d^2 + b_d)y^2 + y^3 + (2b_d + 1)y^2 + (b_d^2 + b_d)y$$

$$oblong[y] * oblong[y + b_d] = y^4 + 2(b_d + 1)y^3 + (b_d^2 + 3b_d + 1)y^2 + (b_d^2 + b_d)y$$

Let us cut the 4th power introducing $(b_d + 1)^2 y^2 - (b_d + 1)^2 y^2 = 0$ in the expression:

$$oblong[y] * oblong[y + b_d]$$

$$= y^4 + 2(b_d + 1)y^3 + (b_d + 1)^2 y^2 - (b_d + 1)^2 y^2 + (b_d^2 + 3b_d + 1)y^2 + (b_d^2 + b_d)y$$

$$oblong[y] * oblong[y + b_d]$$

$$= (y^2 + (b_d + 1)y)^2 - (b_d + 1)^2 y^2 + (b_d^2 + 3b_d + 1)y^2 + (b_d^2 + b_d)y$$

We have:

$$-(b_d + 1)^2 y^2 + (b_d^2 + 3b_d + 1)y^2 = -(b_d^2 + 2b_d + 1)y^2 + (b_d^2 + 3b_d + 1)y^2 = b_d y^2$$

Then

$$oblong[y] * oblong[y + b_d] = ((y + b_d + 1)y)^2 + b_d y^2 + (b_d^2 + b_d)y$$

$$oblong[y] * oblong[y + b_d] = ((y + b_d + 1)y)^2 + b_d y^2 + b_d(b_d + 1)y$$

$$oblong[y] * oblong[y + b_d] = ((y + b_d + 1)y)^2 + b_d((y + b_d + 1)y)$$

Being $x = (y + b_d + 1)y$, then

$$Oblong[y] * Oblong[y + b_d] = (xy)^2 + b_d(xy) = xy(xy + b_d) = Oblong[xy]$$

9.2.2. Using offset $f = 0$:

Let us calculate $oblong[y] * oblong[y + b_d]$ for $oblong[y] = y^2 - y$ in offset $f = 0$:

$$(1) \text{ oblong}[y] = y^2 - y$$

$$\text{oblong}[y + b_d] = (y + b_d)^2 - (y + b_d)$$

$$\text{oblong}[y + b_d] = y^2 + 2b_d y + b_d^2 - y - b_d$$

$$(2) \text{ oblong}[y + b_d] = y^2 + (2b_d - 1)y + b_d^2 - b_d$$

So, (1) * (2) is:

$$\text{oblong}[y] * \text{oblong}[y + b_d] = (y^2 - y)(y^2 + (2b_d - 1)y + b_d^2 - b_d)$$

$$\text{oblong}[y] * \text{oblong}[y + b_d]$$

$$= y^4 + (2b_d - 1)y^3 + (b_d^2 - b_d)y^2 - y^3 - (2b_d - 1)y^2 - (b_d^2 - b_d)y$$

$$\text{oblong}[y] * \text{oblong}[y + b_d] = y^4 + 2(b_d - 1)y^3 + (b_d^2 - 3b_d + 1)y^2 - (b_d^2 - b_d)y$$

Let us cut the 4th power introducing $(b_d - 1)^2 y^2 - (b_d - 1)^2 y^2 = 0$ in the expression:

$$\text{oblong}[y] * \text{oblong}[y + b_d]$$

$$= y^4 + 2(b_d - 1)y^3 + (b_d - 1)^2 y^2 - (b_d - 1)^2 y^2 + (b_d^2 - 3b_d + 1)y^2 - (b_d^2 - b_d)y$$

$$\text{oblong}[y] * \text{oblong}[y + b_d]$$

$$= (y^2 + (b_d - 1)y)^2 - (b_d - 1)^2 y^2 + (b_d^2 - 3b_d + 1)y^2 - (b_d^2 - b_d)y$$

We have:

$$-(b_d - 1)^2 y^2 + (b_d^2 - 3b_d + 1)y^2 = -(b_d^2 - 2b_d + 1)y^2 + (b_d^2 - 3b_d + 1)y^2 = -b_d y^2$$

Then

$$\text{oblong}[y] * \text{oblong}[y + b_d] = ((y + b_d - 1)y)^2 - b_d y^2 - (b_d^2 - b_d)y$$

$$\text{oblong}[y] * \text{oblong}[y + b_d] = ((y + b_d - 1)y)^2 - b_d y^2 - b_d(b_d - 1)y$$

$$\text{oblong}[y] * \text{oblong}[y + b_d] = ((y + b_d - 1)y)^2 - b_d((y + b_d - 1)y)$$

Being $x = (y + b_d - 1)y$ then

$$CG[y] = \text{oblong}[y] * \text{oblong}[y + b_d] = (xy)^2 - b_d(xy) = xy(xy - b_d) = \text{Oblong}[xy]$$

So, the product $\text{oblong}[y] * \text{oblong}[y + b_d]$ is in the form of oblong.

9.3 The quadratic numbers in the form of $y(y \pm b_d)$

Let us study this number form using the offset concepts. So, from the offset study [27], the general quadratic equation in offset zero is:

$$CG_{f=0}[y] = a^0 y^2 + b^0 y + c^0 = ay^2 + (b + 2af)y + (af^2 + bf + c)$$

$$\text{Where } f = \text{roundz} \left[-\frac{b}{2a} \right].$$

$$\text{For } Y[y] = y^2 \pm b_d y \text{ we have } a = 1, b = \pm b_d, c = 0, \text{ and } f = \text{roundz} \left[\mp \frac{b_d}{2} \right].$$

Because of the division by 2, let us separate the analysis for b_d even (in red) and odd (in blue).

For $b_d = 2v$ even:

$$CG[y] = y(y \pm b_d) = y^2 \pm b_d y = y^2 \pm 2vy$$

This equation has $a = 1, b = b_d = \pm 2v, c = 0$, and offset:

$$f = \text{roundz} \left[\mp \frac{2v}{2} \right] = \text{roundz}[\mp v] = \mp v$$

So

$$\begin{aligned}
a^{\circ} &= a = 1 \\
b^{\circ} &= b + 2af = \pm 2v + 2 * 1 * (\mp v) = \pm 2v \mp 2v = 0 \\
c^{\circ} &= af^2 + bf + c = 1 * (\mp v)^2 + (\pm 2v) * (\mp v) + 0 = v^2 - 2v^2 = -v^2 \\
CG_{f=0}[y] &= y^2 - v^2
\end{aligned}$$

Conclusion A: for $b = \text{even} = \pm b_d = \pm 2v$:

$$\begin{aligned}
CG_{f=\mp v}[y] &= y(y \pm 2v) \equiv CG_{f=0}[y] = y^2 - v^2 \\
&= \text{square sequence minus square number}
\end{aligned}$$

For $b_d = 2u - 1$ odd:

We will divide the solution into two parts.

Part I:

$$CG[y] = y(y + b_d) = y^2 + b_d y = y^2 + (2u - 1)y$$

This equation has $a = 1$, $b = b_d = 2u - 1$, $c = 0$, and offset:

$$f = \text{roundz} \left[-\frac{b_d}{2 * 1} \right] = \text{roundz} \left[-\frac{2u - 1}{2} \right] = \text{roundz}[-u + 0.5] = -u$$

So

$$\begin{aligned}
a^{\circ} &= a = 1 \\
b^{\circ} &= b + 2af = 2u - 1 + 2 * 1 * (-u) = -1 \\
c^{\circ} &= af^2 + bf + c = 1 * (-u)^2 + (2u - 1) * (-u) + 0 = u^2 - 2u^2 + u = -(u^2 - u) \\
CG_{f=0}[y] &= y^2 - y - (u^2 - u)
\end{aligned}$$

Conclusion I for $b = \text{odd} = b_d = 2u - 1$:

$$\begin{aligned}
CG_{f=-u}[y] &= y(y + (2u - 1)) \equiv CG_{f=0}[y] = (y^2 - y) - (u^2 - u) \\
&= \text{oblong sequence minus oblong number}
\end{aligned}$$

Part II:

$$CG[y] = y(y - b_d) = y^2 - y = y^2 - (2u - 1)y$$

This equation has $a = 1$, $b = -b_d = -(2u - 1)$, $c = 0$, and offset:

$$f = \text{roundz} \left[-\frac{-b_d}{2 * 1} \right] = \text{roundz} \left[\frac{2u - 1}{2} \right] = \text{roundz}[u - 0.5] = u - 1$$

So

$$\begin{aligned}
a^{\circ} &= a = 1 \\
b^{\circ} &= b + 2af = -2u + 1 + 2 * 1 * (u - 1) = -1 \\
c^{\circ} &= af^2 + bf + c = 1 * (u - 1)^2 + (-2u + 1) * (u - 1) + 0 \\
&= u^2 - 2u + 1 - 2u^2 + 2u + u - 1 = -(u^2 - u) \\
CG_{f=0}[y] &= y^2 - y - (u^2 - u)
\end{aligned}$$

Conclusion II for $b = \text{odd} = -b_d = -(2u - 1)$:

$$\begin{aligned}
CG_{f=u-1}[y] &= y(y - (2u - 1)) \equiv CG_{f=0}[y] = (y^2 - y) - (u^2 - u) \\
&= \text{oblong sequence minus oblong number}
\end{aligned}$$

Conclusion B: for $b = \text{odd} = \pm b_d = \pm(2u - 1)$:

$$\begin{aligned}
CG_{f \neq 0}[y] &= y(y \pm (2u - 1)) \equiv CG_{f=0}[y] = (y^2 - y) - (u^2 - u) \\
&= \text{oblong sequence minus oblong number}
\end{aligned}$$

Examples:

1. $CG[y] = y(y \pm 6)$. Because $b_d = 2v = 6$ is an even number, then $v = 3$, $c^o = -v^2 = -9$. So, $CG[y] = y(y \pm 6) \equiv CG_{f=0}[y] = y^2 - 9$.
2. $CG[y] = y(y \pm 7)$. Because $b = 2u - 1 = 7$ is an odd number, then $u = 4$, $c^o = -(u^2 - u) = -12$. So, $CG[y] = y(y \pm 7) \equiv CG_{f=0}[y] = y^2 - y - 12$. A 2nd way to find the value of the c^o coefficient when the $b = \text{odd number}$ coefficient is to divide it by 2 and then multiply the floor and ceiling of the result. So, $\frac{b}{2} = \frac{7}{2} = 3.5$, and $[3.5] * [3.5] = 3 * 4 = 12$.

9.4 Conclusion for products of two oblong numbers:

The product of two oblong numbers is a composite generator that obeys these laws:

1. For $\pm b_d = \pm 0$, we have $b = \text{even}$, $v = 0$, $v^2 = 0$, then $oblong[y] * oblong[y \pm 0]$ is in the form of square number.
2. For $\pm b_d = \pm 1$, we have $b = \text{odd}$, $u = 1$, $u^2 - u = 0$, then, $oblong[y] * oblong[y \pm 1]$ is in the form of oblong number.
3. For $\pm b_d = \pm 2$, we have $b = \text{even}$, $v = 1$, $v^2 = 1$, then, $oblong[y] * oblong[y \pm 2]$ is in the form of (square-1) number.
4. For $\pm b_d = \pm 3$, we have $b = \text{odd}$, $u = 2$, $u^2 - u = 2$, then, $oblong[y] * oblong[y \pm 3]$ is in the form of (oblong-2) number.
5. For $\pm b_d = \pm 4$, we have $b = \text{even}$, $v = 2$, $v^2 = 4$, then, $oblong[y] * oblong[y \pm 4]$ is in the form of (square-4) number.
6. For $\pm b_d = \pm 5$, we have $b = \text{odd}$, $u = 3$, $u^2 - u = 6$, then, $oblong[y] * oblong[y \pm 5]$ is in the form of (oblong-6) number.
7. For $\pm b_d = \pm 6$, we have $b = \text{even}$, $v = 3$, $v^2 = 9$, then, $oblong[y] * oblong[y \pm 6]$ is in the form of (square-9) number.
8. For $\pm b_d = \pm 7$, we have $b = \text{odd}$, $u = 4$, $u^2 - u = 12$, then, $oblong[y] * oblong[y \pm 7]$ is in the form of (oblong-12) number.
9. And so on...

Conclusion II:

For $b_d = \text{even}$, $oblong[y] * oblong[y \pm b_d]$ is in the form of (square sequence minus square number), where the square number is $\left(\frac{b_d}{2}\right)^2$. It is $\left(\text{https://oeis.org/A000290} - \left(\frac{b_d}{2}\right)^2\right)$.

For $b_d = \text{odd}$, $oblong[y] * oblong[y \pm b_d]$ is in the form of an (oblong sequence minus oblong number) where the oblong number is $\frac{b_d-1}{2} * \frac{b_d+1}{2}$. $\left(\text{https://oeis.org/A002378} - \frac{b_d-1}{2} * \frac{b_d+1}{2}\right)$.

9.5 The products between square and oblong numbers

Since the products of two squares are other squares and the products of 2 oblongs have two shapes that depend on the offset (“index distance” b_d) between the two oblong factors, then what are the shapes that appear because of multiplying a square number by an oblong number?

Looking for the square form

Being

$$\text{oblong}[y] = y^2 - y$$

$$\text{square}[y + b_d] = (y + b_d)^2 = y^2 + 2b_d y + b_d^2$$

Then

$$\text{square}[y + b_d] * \text{oblong}[y] = (y^2 + 2b_d y + b_d^2)(y^2 - y)$$

$$\text{square}[y + b_d] * \text{oblong}[y] = y^4 + 2b_d y^3 + b_d^2 y^2 - y^3 - 2b_d y^2 - b_d^2 y$$

$$\text{square}[y + b_d] * \text{oblong}[y] = y^4 - y^3 + 2b_d y^3 - 2b_d y^2 + b_d^2 y^2 - b_d^2 y$$

$$\text{square}[y + b_d] * \text{oblong}[y] = (y^4 - y^3) + 2b_d(y^3 - y^2) + b_d^2(y^2 - y)$$

$$\text{square}[y + b_d] * \text{oblong}[y] = (y - 1)y^3 + 2b_d(y - 1)y^2 + b_d^2(y - 1)y$$

$$\text{square}[y + b_d] * \text{oblong}[y] = (y^3 + 2b_d y^2 + b_d^2 y)(y - 1)$$

$$\text{square}[y + b_d] * \text{oblong}[y] = (y^2 + 2b_d y + b_d^2)y(y - 1)$$

$$\text{square}[y + b_d] * \text{oblong}[y] = (y^2 + 2b_d y + b_d^2)(y^2 - y)$$

$$\text{square}[y + b_d] * \text{oblong}[y] = (y + b_d)^2(y^2 - y)$$

There is no way to have the product square number times oblong numbers in the function of square numbers.

Looking for the oblong form

However, if we do:

$$\text{square}[y + b_d] * \text{oblong}[y] = (y + b_d)^2(y^2 - y)$$

$$\text{square}[y + b_d] * \text{oblong}[y] = (y + b_d)^2 y^2 - (y + b_d)^2 y$$

$$\text{square}[y + b_d] * \text{oblong}[y] = \text{square} * y^2 - \text{square} * y$$

Being $(y + b_d) = j$:

$$\text{square}[y + b_d] * \text{oblong}[y] = j^2 y^2 - j^2 y$$

$$\text{square}[y + b_d] * \text{oblong}[y] = j^2 y(y - 1)$$

$$\text{square}[y + b_d] * \text{oblong}[y] = \frac{4j^2 y(y - 1)}{4}$$

$$\text{square}[y + b_d] * \text{oblong}[y] = \frac{2j^2 y(2y - 2)}{4}$$

$$\text{square}[y + b_d] * \text{oblong}[y] = \frac{j^2(2y(2y - 2))}{4}$$

Being $2y = k$:

$$\text{square}[y + b_d] * \text{oblong}[y] = \frac{j^2(k(k-2))}{4}$$

Being $k = m + 1$:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{square}[y + b_d] * \text{oblong}[y] &= \frac{j^2(m-1)(m+1)}{4} \\ \text{square}[y + b_d] * \text{oblong}[y] &= \frac{j^2(m^2-1)}{4} = \left(\frac{j}{2}\right)^2 (m^2-1) \end{aligned}$$

Then, bringing back to y :

$$\text{square}[y + b_d] * \text{oblong}[y] = \left(\frac{y + b_d}{2}\right)^2 ((2y-1)^2 - 1)$$

Since we cannot guarantee that the term $\frac{y+b_d}{2}$ is always an integer, then

$$\text{square}[y + b_d] * \text{oblong}[y] = \left(\frac{y + b_d}{2}\right)^2 * ((\text{odd square}) - 1)$$

Conclusion III: we can always put the product square number times the oblong number as a function of $(\text{odd square} - 1)$ number.

$(\text{odd square} - 1)$ numbers are <https://oeis.org/A000290> $[2n - 1] - 1 =$ <https://oeis.org/A016754> $[n] - 1 =$ <https://oeis.org/A033996> $[n]$

9.6 The oblong numbers in the function of the (square-1) numbers

Because

$$\text{square}[y + b_d] * \text{Oblong}[y] = \left(\frac{y + b_d}{2}\right)^2 ((2y-1)^2 - 1)$$

Then, if the make $y + b_d = 1$, then

$$\text{square}[1] * \text{oblong}[y] = \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^2 ((2y-1)^2 - 1) =$$

Because $\text{square}[1] = 1$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{oblong}[y] &= y^2 - y = \frac{(2y-1)^2 - 1}{4} \\ \text{oblong}[y] &= y^2 - y = \frac{(\text{odd square}) - 1}{4} = \text{even number} \end{aligned}$$

Conclusion IV: all oblong numbers are in the form of $\frac{((\text{odd square})-1)}{4}$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{https://oeis.org/A002378}[n] &= \frac{\text{https://oeis.org/A000290}[2n - 1] - 1}{4} \\ &= \frac{\text{https://oeis.org/A016754}[n] - 1}{4} = \frac{\text{https://oeis.org/A033996}[n]}{4} \end{aligned}$$

9.7 The special case: 4 times oblong numbers

Because

$$\text{oblong}[y] = y^2 - y = \frac{(2y - 1)^2 - 1}{4}$$

Then

$$4 * \text{oblong}[y] = 4y^2 - 4y = (2y - 1)^2 - 1 = (\text{odd square}) - 1 = \text{even}$$

Conclusion V: all $4 * \text{oblong}$ numbers are in the form of an even $((\text{odd square}) - 1)$ number.

$$\begin{aligned} 4 * \text{https://oeis.org/A002378}[n] &= \text{https://oeis.org/A000290}[2n - 1] - 1 \\ &= \text{https://oeis.org/A016754}[n] - 1 = \text{https://oeis.org/A033996}[n] \end{aligned}$$

9.8 The sum of 2 squares, the sum of 2 oblongs

See all even square numbers can be written in the form of two times the sum of two square numbers and all odd square numbers can be written in the form of the twice of the sum of two oblong numbers plus 1 at <https://www.mersenneforum.org/showthread.php?t=27892>.

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References

- [1] Aaronson, Scott. (2003) “The prime Facts: From Euclid to AKS”, available online at <http://www.scottaaronson.com/writings/prime.pdf>.
- [2] Abdul-Baki, Bassam. (2005) "Extended Midy's Theorem", available online at http://www.abdulgabi.org/math/midys_theorem.pdf.
- [3] Babbage, Charles. (1791-1871) "Babbage's Difference Engine, Principle of the difference Engines", CHM Computer History Museum, available online at <https://www.computerhistory.org/babbage/howitworks>.
- [4] Belden, Otto. "Going's on of Otto's Pastimes", available online at <http://ottobelden.blogspot.com/2010/10/number-sequences-with-ms-excel-visual.html>.
- [5] Caldwell, Chris K. (20xx) "Prime Curios!", available online at <https://primes.utm.edu/curios/>.
- [6] Cox, David N. (2008) "Visualizing the Sieve of Eratosthenes". Notices of the American Mathematical Society. Volume 55, issue 5, page 579, available online at <https://www.ams.org/notices/200805/tx080500579p.pdf>.
- [7] Crawford, Tom. (2023) “Parabolic Mirrors – Numberphile”. Available online at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oSXVmuNifRI&t=459s>.
- [8] Evard, Jean-Claude. (2018) "How to find central pairs of complementary divisors of n?", <https://www.researchgate.net/post/How-to-find-central-pairs-of-complementary-divisors-of-n>.
- [9] Gang, Xiao. "Two squares", available online at http://wims.unice.fr/~wims/en_tool~number~twosquares.en.html.
- [10] Gathen, Joachim & Gerhard, Jürgen. (1997). Fast Algorithms for Taylor Shifts and Certain Difference Equations. Proceedings of the International Symposium on Symbolic and Algebraic Computation, ISSAC. 40-47. 10.1145/258726.258745. Available online at file:///C:/Users/charl/Downloads/Fast_Algorithms_for_Taylor_Shifts_and_Certain_Diff.pdf.
- [11] Gil, Juan B. and Weiner, Michael D. (2006) "On Cyclic Numbers and an Extension of Midy's Theorem", <https://arxiv.org/abs/math/0605347>.

- [12] Grime, James. (2013) "Prime Spirals - Numberphile", available online at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iFuR97YcSLM>.
- [13] Gupta, Ankit. (2005) "Decimal Expansion of $1/P$ and Subgroup Sums", available online at <https://www.emis.de/journals/INTEGERS/papers/f19/f19.pdf>.
- [14] Iniguez, Jose C. (2016) "The Golden Quadratic and the Fibonacci System III", available online at https://www.researchgate.net/publication/293175494_The_Golden_Quadratic_and_the_Fibonacci_System_III.
- [15] Johnson, Jeremy R. and Krandick, Werner and Ruslanov, Anatole D. (2005) "Architecture-Aware Classical Taylor Shift by 1", available online at <https://www.cs.drexel.edu/files/ts467/DU-CS-05-06.pdf>.
- [16] Jones, Gareth A. and Jones, J. Mary, "Elementary Number Theory", Springer, 1998; pp. 221-222.
- [17] Kircheri, P. Athanasii. (1664) "Mundus Subterraneus", pg. 24, https://archive.org/details/athanasiikircher00kirc_4/page/n53/mode/2up?ref=ol&view=theater.
- [18] Klauber, Laurence Monroe. (1931), "Klauber's Triangle" pg. 362 available online at <https://archive.org/stream/1931fieldnotesla00klau#page/362/mode/1up>.
- [19] Knill, Oliver. (Jun 19, 2016) "Some Experiments in Number Theory", available online at <http://people.math.harvard.edu/~knill/primes/papers/gaussian.pdf>.
- [20] Kusniec, Charles. (2023). Symbolic Conventions and Lexicon. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10127987>.
- [21] Kusniec, Charles (2023). Exploring Hyperbolic Patterns in the Map of Integers and Divisors (MID) Framework. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10258328>.
- [22] Kusniec, Charles. (2023). Exploring Parabolic Patterns in the Map of Integers and Divisors (MID) Framework. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10252480>.
- [23] Kusniec, Charles (2023). The SOM Numbers (part I). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10208029>.
- [24] Kusniec, Charles. (2023). The TSP - Triangular Sieve of Primes. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10155610>.
- [25] Kusniec, Charles. (2023). Divisor Trek. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10128279>.
- [26] Kusniec, Charles. (2023). Integers are only Primes and Composites. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8419643>.
- [27] Kusniec, Charles. (2023). Shift, Symmetry, and Asymmetry in Polynomial Sequences. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8433336>.

- [28] Kusniec, Charles. (2023). The Hyperbolic Sieve of Primes (HSP). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8419575>.
- [29] Kusniec, Charles. (2023). The Modular Hyperbolic Sieve of Primes (MHSP). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10109568>.
- [30] Kusniec, Charles. (2023). The Polynomial Simplest Equations, the Symmetry Point, the Two Simplest Recurrence Equations, and the Method of Differences. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8434817>.
- [31] Kusniec, Charles. (2020) "Conventions, Notations, and Abbreviations", EasyChair preprint no. 4554, available online at <https://easychair.org/publications/preprint/4ZDm>.
- [32] Kusniec, Charles. (2020) "Hyperboctys", EasyChair preprint no. 4553, available online at <https://easychair.org/publications/preprint/RNvX>.
- [33] Kusniec, Charles. (2020) "Offset in Quadratics", EasyChair preprint no. 4428, available online at <https://easychair.org/publications/preprint/FQgX>.
- [34] Kusniec, Charles. (2020) "Paraboctys (part 1)", EasyChair preprint no. 4430, available online at <https://easychair.org/publications/preprint/rSJd>.
- [35] Kusniec, Charles. (2020) "Paraboctys (part 2)", EasyChair preprint no. 4482, available online at <https://easychair.org/publications/preprint/7n9N>.
- [36] Kusniec, Charles. (2020) "Paraboctys (part 3)", EasyChair preprint no. 4555, available online at <https://easychair.org/publications/preprint/hd87>.
- [37] Kusniec, Charles. (2020) "Quadratics Classification", EasyChair preprint no. 4429, available online at <https://easychair.org/publications/preprint/KRpp>.
- [38] Kusniec, Charles. (2020) "The adjustable hyperbolic paraboloid framework of the integer numbers (Part 1)", EasyChair preprint no. 4667, available online at <https://easychair.org/publications/preprint/Ps32>.
- [39] Kusniec, Charles. (2020) "The adjustable hyperbolic paraboloid framework of the integer numbers (Part 2)", EasyChair preprint no. 4733, available online at <https://easychair.org/publications/preprint/l731>.
- [40] Kusniec, Charles. (2020) "The Hyperbolic Sieve of Primes and Divisors", EasyChair preprint no. 4426, available online at <https://easychair.org/publications/preprint/lCgH>.
- [41] Kusniec, Charles. (2020) "The Hyperbolic Sieve of Primes and Products xy ", EasyChair preprint no. 4427, available online at <https://easychair.org/publications/preprint/SbFH>.
- [42] Kusniec, Charles. (2020) "The Polynomial Simplest Equations, the Symmetry Point, the Two Simplest Recurrence Equations, and the Method of Differences", EasyChair preprint no. 4423, available online at <https://easychair.org/publications/preprint/qr3P>.
- [43] Lauritzen, Bill. "The Social Applications of Highly Composite Numbers", available online at <http://www.earth360.com/math-versatile.html>.

- [44] Lewittes, Joseph. (2007) "Midy's Theorem for Periodic Decimals", available online at <http://www.kurims.kyoto-u.ac.jp/EMIS/journals/INTEGERS/papers/h2/h2.pdf>.
- [45] Lo, Joseph. "Hyperbolic paraboloid", available online at http://www.math.ubc.ca/~cwsei/math200/graphics/hyperbolic_paraboloid.html.
- [46] Loh, Po-Shen. Daily Challenge with Po-Shen Loh. (2019) "Examples: A Different Way to Solve Quadratic Formulas", available online at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XKBX0r3J-9Y>.
- [47] Martin, Harold W. (2007) "Generalizations of Midy's Theorem on Repeating Decimals", available online at <https://www.emis.de/journals/INTEGERS/papers/h3/h3.pdf>.
- [48] Mathematics, StackExchange. (2015) "Meaning of Rays in Polar Plot of Prime Numbers", available online at <https://math.stackexchange.com/questions/885879/meaning-of-rays-in-polar-plot-of-prime-numbers>.
- [49] Mathematics, StackExchange. (2016) "How to force prime numbers into a line?", available online at <https://math.stackexchange.com/questions/1291787/how-to-force-prime-numbers-into-a-line>.
- [50] Matiyasevich, Yuri and Stechkin, Boris. (1999) "A visual Sieve for Prime Numbers", available online at <https://logic.pdmi.ras.ru/~yumat/personaljournal/sieve/sieve.html>.
- [51] Medina, Miguel Ángel Morales ([^]DiAmOnD[^]). (2006) "142857: Un número realmente interesante", available online at <https://www.gaussianos.com/142857-un-numero-realmente-interesante/>.
- [52] Medina, Miguel Ángel Morales ([^]DiAmOnD[^]). (2013) "La sorprendente criba de la parábola", available online at https://www.gaussianos.com/la-sorprendente-criba-de-la-parabola/?utm_source=feedburner&utm_medium=feed&utm_campaign=Feed%3A+gaussianos+%28Gaussianos%29.
- [53] Miska, Piotr and Ulas, Maciej, "On Consecutive 1's In Continued Fractions Expansions of Square Roots of Prime Numbers", available online at <https://arxiv.org/abs/1904.03404>.
- [54] Munafo, Robert. (1996-2020) "Sequence A002061, Hogben's Centered Polygonal Numbers", available online at <http://mrob.com/pub/seq/a002061.html>.
- [55] Munafo, Robert. (1996-2020) "Sequence A006542, $C(n,3)C(n-1,3)/4$ ", available online at <http://mrob.com/pub/seq/a006542.html>.
- [56] Nicholes, Will. "Math and numbers", available online at <http://willnicholes.com/math/index.htm>.
- [57] O'Dell, Eric. (1996-2021) "Ulam Spiral Explorer", available online at <https://meresh.com/ulam.html>.
- [58] OEIS Foundation Inc. (2021), "The On-Line Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences". Published electronically at <http://oeis.org>.

- [59] Paris, Carlos. (2009) "Primal Chaos (Visualizations)", available online at <http://www.sievesofchaos.com/>.
- [60] Pegg, Ed Jr. "Bouniakowsky Conjecture", from MathWorld--A Wolfram Web Resource, created by Eric W. Weisstein. <https://mathworld.wolfram.com/BouniakowskyConjecture.html>.
- [61] Pegg, Ed Jr. (2006) "Prime Generating Polynomials, Math Games", available online at http://www.mathpuzzle.com/MAA/48-Prime%20Generating%20Polynomials/mathgames_07_17_06.html.
- [62] Pol, Omar Evaristo. (2001-2007), "Sobre el patrón de los números primos", available online at <http://www.polprimos.com/>.
- [63] Pol, Omar Evaristo. (2009-2012) "Links with illustrations", available online in the sequences <https://oeis.org/A027750> , <https://oeis.org/A056538> , <https://oeis.org/A193829> , <https://oeis.org/A212119>.
- [64] Polster, Burkard - Mathologer. (2016) "Infinite fractions and the most irrational number", available online at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CaasbfdJdJg>.
- [65] Rabahy, David. "Google Sheets", available online at https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1GPqipwaQUbD_mPtyJITV8CCJeEjUOKMXz9fVDXAt3Ws/edit#gid=0.
- [66] Ribenboim, Paulo. (2004) "The Little Book of Bigger Primes".
- [67] Ross, Michael M. (2007-2015) "Natural Numbers", available online at <http://www.naturalnumbers.org>.
- [68] Sacks, Robert. (2003-2007) "NumberSpiral.com", available online at <http://www.numberpiral.com/index.html>.
- [69] Sanderson, Grant (3Blue1Brown). (2019) "Why do prime numbers make these spirals?", available online at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EK32jo7i5LQ>.
- [70] Sanderson, Grant (3Blue1Brown). (2023) "The Prime Number Race" - Numberphile, available online at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YAsHGOWB408>.
- [71] Sato, Takumi. (2013) "Classification of natural numbers and the four sequences", available online at https://www.researchgate.net/publication/358139258_Classification_of_natural_numbers_and_the_four_sequences.
- [72] Schildbach, Wolfgang. "Patterns in prime numbers?", available online at <https://www.fermi.franken.de/wschildbach/primes.html#java>.
- [73] Shannon, A. G. and Leyendekkers, J. V. (2017) "On Legendre's Conjecture", available online at <https://nntdm.net/papers/nntdm-23/NNTDM-23-2-117-125.pdf>.

- [74] Shaw, Mary and Traub, J.F. (1974) "On the number of multiplications for the evaluation of a polynomial and some of its derivatives", available online at <https://dl.acm.org/doi/pdf/10.1145/321796.321810>.
- [75] Siano, D. B. and Siano, J. D. (1994) "An Algorithm for Generating Highly Composite Numbers", available online at <http://wwwhomes.uni-bielefeld.de/achim/julianmanuscript3.pdf>.
- [76] Sloane, Neil J. A. at Numberphile video by Brady Haran. (Apr 13, 2021) "Eureka Sequences", available online at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6X2D497is6Y>.
- [77] Sparks, Ben at Numberphile video by Brady Haran. (2018) "The Golden Ratio (why it is so irrational)", available online at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sj8Sg8qjOg&t=642s>.
- [78] StackExchange, Mathematics. (2014) "Polynomial shift", available online at <https://math.stackexchange.com/questions/694565/polynomial-shift>.
- [79] Stapel, Elizabeth. "Conics: Hyperbolae: Introduction", Purplemath, available from <https://www.purplemath.com/modules/hyperbola.htm>.
- [80] Stapel, Elizabeth. "Finding the Next Number in a Sequence: The Method of Common Differences", Purplemath, available from <https://www.purplemath.com/modules/nextnumb.htm>.
- [81] Unacademy Learning App, (?) "Rectangular Hyperbola", available online at <https://player.uacdn.net/lesson-raw/53KRIOKDC4WS1UKP233U/pdf/9971677413.pdf>.
- [82] Ventrella, Jeffrey. (2007) "Divisor Drips and Square Root Waves", available online at <http://www.divisorplot.com/>.
- [83] Viète, François. (1540-1603) "Formule de Viète", available online at https://edugemath.ch/1re/ch7/ma1-ch7-docs-cours/Ma1_Ch7-degre2_Viete.pdf and <http://serge.mehl.free.fr/chrono/Viete.html>.
- [84] Weisstein, Eric W. "Digital Root", from MathWorld--A Wolfram Web Resource. <https://mathworld.wolfram.com/DigitalRoot.html>.
- [85] Weisstein, Eric W. "Dirichlet's Theorem", from MathWorld--A Wolfram Web Resource. <https://mathworld.wolfram.com/DirichletsTheorem.html>.
- [86] Weisstein, Eric W. "Heegner Number", from MathWorld--A Wolfram Web Resource. <https://mathworld.wolfram.com/HeegnerNumber.html>.
- [87] Weisstein, Eric W. "Lucky Number of Euler", from MathWorld--A Wolfram Web Resource. <https://mathworld.wolfram.com/LuckyNumberofEuler.html>.
- [88] Weisstein, Eric W. "Powerfree", from MathWorld--A Wolfram Web Resource. <https://mathworld.wolfram.com/Powerfree.html>.

- [89] Weisstein, Eric W. "Prime Spiral", from MathWorld--A Wolfram Web Resource.
<https://mathworld.wolfram.com/PrimeSpiral.html>.
- [90] Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia, available online at
<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Portal:Mathematics>.
- [91] Williamson, John. "Number Spirals", available online at
<http://www.dcs.gla.ac.uk/~jhw/spirals/index.html>.